

Stannous chloride dihydrate-mediated efficient access to secondary and primary amides from oximes[†]

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Abstract : Highly selective, efficient and expeditious Beckmann rearrangement of a wide range of ketoximes to secondary amides (20 examples) has been accomplished using stoichiometric amount of stannous chloride dihydrate in the presence of nucleophilic additive, tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide (TBAI) (10 mol%) and 4 Å MS in dry acetonitrile at reflux temperature. Aldoximes delivered primary amides through intermediacy of nitriles upon heating with an equimolar amount of SnCl₂·2H₂O and DBU in dry toluene at reflux in good to acceptable yields (12 examples). Utilization of mild Lewis acid, inexpensive reagents and procedural simplicity including easy isolation of products are key advantageous features of the protocol.

Keywords : Oximes, primary and secondary amides, Beckmann rearrangement, stannous chloride dihydrate, TBAI, DBU.

Introduction

Amide functionality is ubiquitous in pharmaceuticals, drug intermediates and industrially important raw materials for plastics, detergents and lubricants¹. Efficient generation of amide bond by atom- and step-economic methods utilizing safe reagents has been recently identified as a high priority area in green chemistry initiatives². The Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes allow straightforward simple access to the huge chemical space of amides and amines. It primarily relies on electrophilic activation of oximic hydroxyl group for its departure as a prelude to the rearrangement. However, traditional activators used for this purpose such as concentrated H₂SO₄, PCl₅, HCl-HOAc-Ac₂O, POCl₃³ are often required in excess under harsh reaction conditions. These procedures are incompatible with acid-sensitive functionalities and generate huge amount of ammonium/metal sulfate waste during isolation of amides, particularly in large scale operations⁴. Contemporary emphasis on environmentally benign processes led to the development of several liquid phase, vapour phase and solvent-free protocols. Utilization of organocatalysts such as oxalic acid⁵, chloral hydrate⁶, sulphamic acid⁷, bis(2-oxo-3-oxazolidinyl)phosphinic chlo-

ride⁸, cyanuric chloride⁹, diethylchlorophosphate¹⁰, triphosphazene¹¹, *O*-alkyl-*N,N*-dimethylformamidium salt¹², 1-chlorocyclopropenium ion¹³, mild Lewis acid catalysts such as FeCl₃¹⁴, Ga(OTf)₃¹⁵, HgCl₂¹⁶ and I₂¹⁷ represent some successful recent approaches. Supercritical water¹⁸, ionic liquids with Brønsted acidity¹⁹ were explored as alternative green media with mixed success. In continuation of our earlier works in this area^{17,20}, we identified stannous chloride dihydrate as an attractive candidate for this purpose in view of its attenuated Lewis acidity, compatibility with hydroxy group^{21a} and ability to coordinate with both oximic nitrogen and hydroxyl group. The utility of stannous chloride has been demonstrated for several important organic transformations such as esterification^{21b}, directed stereoselective aldol condensation^{22a}, Biginelli synthesis²³, allylation of hydroxycarbonyl compounds²⁴, synthesis of vicinal diols²⁵, novel polycyclic heterocycles by tandem deacetalization-bicyclization²⁶ and homoallylic alcohols²⁷. The activation of mild Lewis acids such as SnCl₂²⁷, CeCl₃·7H₂O²⁸ by iodide additives is well precedented. We were intrigued to evaluate the role of TBAI to modulate the reactivity of SnCl₂·2H₂O in the present context.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Herein, we describe hitherto unexplored $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -mediated Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes and transformation of aryl aldoximes to primary amides via aryl nitriles.

Results and discussion

For a preliminary examination of feasibility of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a reagent for Beckmann transformation, acetophenone oxime (**1**) was chosen as a model substrate and submitted to reaction with it under various conditions. Acetonitrile is reported to be the solvent of choice for several Lewis acid-catalyzed Beckmann rearrangements due to its stabilizing influence on the incipient carbenium ion intermediate on route to amides^{7,15,16}. Sn^{II} reagents usually exhibit good solubility in acetonitrile and propionitrile due to their strong coordination with the nitrile group^{22b}. We focused on dry solvents for conducting optimization experiments to eliminate or minimize the possibility of undesirable hydrolytic cleavage of **1**.

The results of these experiments are presented in Table 1.

Heating **1** with a catalytic amount of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.1 mmol), with or without TBAI, resulted in recovery of most of the starting material and poor conversion to acetanilide (**1a**) together with acetophenone (**1b**) (entries 1, 2). Increment in the amount of the reagent to 50 mol% substantially enhanced the reaction rate and improved the yield of **1a**. However, concomitant deoxygenation could not be eliminated altogether (entries 3, 4). Exposure of the oxime to stoichiometric amount of the reagent in combination with TBAI (0.1 mmol) further biased the reaction in favour of Beckmann rearrangement (entry 6). Surprisingly, there was substantial erosion of selectivity when a reagent combination of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and TBAI in 1 : 1 ratio was employed (entry 9). The dismal performance seems to stem, at least in part, from the release of entire water content of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by ligand exchange by iodide ion, thereby favouring deoxygenation at the expense

Table 1. Optimization experiments on $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -mediated Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes

The reaction scheme shows acetophenone oxime (**1**) reacting with $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to produce acetanilide (**1a**) and acetophenone (**1b**).

Entry	$\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (mmol)	TBAI (mmol)	Solvent additive, if any	Reaction ^a time	Yield ^b of amide 1a (%)	Yield ^b of parent ketone 1b (%)
1	0.1	–	CH_3CN	6 h	8 ^c	15
2	0.1	0.1	CH_3CN	6 h	10 ^c	17
3	0.5	0.1	CH_3CN	2 h	70	5
4	0.5	0.5	CH_3CN	3 h	65	10
5	1	–	CH_3CN	40 min	80	10
6	1	0.1	CH_3CN	20 min	90	6
7	1	0.1	–	20 min	40	45
8	1	0.5	CH_3CN	1.5 h	80	12
9	1	1	CH_3CN	3 h	30	40
10	1	0.1	CeCN , 4 Å MS	30 min	98	–
11	1	0.1	Toluene, 4 Å MS	4 h	90	–
12	1	0.1	EtOH	4 h	30	15
13	1	0.1	THF	4 h	85	–

^aReaction conditions : Reactions were carried out on one millimolar scale in dry acetonitrile/other solvents (3 mL/mmol) under refluxing conditions.

^bRefers to isolated yield upon column chromatographic purification.

^cFor entries 1 and 2, unreacted starting material was also recovered along with meager amounts of amides and ketone.

of amide formation (eq. (1))²⁹.

To address the selectivity issue arising out of deoxygenation we decided to utilize the desiccant 4 Å molecular sieve as additive. Gratifyingly, hydrolytic rupture of the oxime was totally suppressed upon heating **1** with SnCl₂·2H₂O (1 mmol) and TBAI (0.1 mmol) in dry acetonitrile at reflux with 4 Å MS and the amide was delivered in an impressive yield of 98% in 30 min (entry 10). We screened dry toluene, ethanol and THF as alternative reaction me-

dia. Ethanol turned out to be most disappointing in terms of selectivity and yield of amide. Toluene and THF fared much better and afforded acetanilide, albeit slowly, in excellent yield and free from acetophenone (entries 11, 13). The optimized reaction condition [SnCl₂·2H₂O (1 mol equiv.), TBAI (0.1 mol equiv.), dry CH₃CN, 4 Å MS] was applied to diversely substituted ketoximes with success, demonstrating the scope and generality of the procedure. The results of the experiments are summarized in Table 2.

Acetophenone oximes bearing moderately activating OMe, Cl, allyloxy or electroneutral methyl group gave

Table 2. SnCl₂·2H₂O-mediated Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes in the presence of TBAI and 4 Å MS

Entry	Ketoximes	Reaction time ^a	Product (1a-20a , 15b , 16b)	Yield (%) ^b
1		30 min		98
2		30 min		96
3		2 h		95
4		1 h		92
5		3 h		80
6		6 h		62
7		30 min		90
8		1 h		82
9		30 min		85

10		65		
11		57		
12		76		
13		72		
14		95		
15		19 + 68		
16		40 + 55		
17		94		
18		96		
19		60		
20		97		

^aReaction conditions : SnCl₂·2H₂O (2 mmol), DBU (2 mmol), dry toluene (6 mL), reflux.

^bRefers to isolated yield after chromatographic purification; the primary amides and aldehydes are known products with physical and spectral properties that agreed closely with those reported in literature.

amides expeditiously in excellent yields (entries 2, 4, 7, 8, 9). Interestingly, 2-aminoacetophenone oxime yielded the purine **6a** in a sluggish reaction (entry 6). The forma-

tion of **6a** implied heterocyclization involving interception of the initially formed amide by *o*-amino group. However, no such heterocyclization was observed with

its hydroxy counterpart (entry 12). In the case of benzophenones, the optimized reaction condition also proved successful. Unsymmetrically substituted benzophenone oximes **15** and **16** provided a mixture of amides and the predominant product in each case was the result of migration of the aryl group with greater migratory aptitude. Inasmuch as the *E/Z*-equilibration for benzophenone oximes is sterically more demanding than that of acetophenone oximes, this result is consistent with stereoselective *anti* migration from the respective *E*- and *Z*-oximes that constitute the starting material. Remarkably, the *E*-, *Z*-isomerization is often found to be faster than the rearrangement in several existing methods¹⁵ including the I₂-mediated protocol developed by us¹⁷. The protocol worked well when the migrating group was 2-thiophenyl and for α,β -unsaturated ketoxime (entries 17, 20). The conversion of cyclohexanone oxime to ϵ -caprolactam, one of the most industrially important applications of Beckmann rearrangement, was accomplished in an acceptable yield of 60% in 30 min (entry 19).

The rearrangement of aldoximes to provide primary amides is normally precluded due to poor migratory aptitude of hydrogen. The conversion has been accomplished by dehydration of aldoximes to nitriles, followed by con-

trolled hydration to primary amides under Rh³⁰, Ru^{31a}, Ir^{31b} and Au-Ag catalysis³². It was our interest to evaluate the scope of the Sn^{II}-based isomerization of aldoximes to primary amides as cost-effective alternative to these protocols using costly and exotic reagents. However, the representative aldoxime, piperonal oxime (**2**) underwent rapid deoximation with SnCl₂·2H₂O (1 mmol) in acetonitrile under reflux (entry 1, Table 3). To our satisfaction, the desired primary amide was obtained in an acceptable yield of 75% upon heating **2** with a mixture of SnCl₂·2H₂O and diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU) in equimolar ratio (entry 2). Other nitrogen bases such as Et₃N and pyridine were also screened as alternatives to DBU but DBU surpassed them (higher yield of amide and selectivity). This is possibly due to deactivation of SnCl₂ by their strong coordination with Sn^{II}, which is not possible for DBU due to its sterically hindered and non-nucleophilic nature. The abstraction of the aldehydic hydrogen by the potent base DBU coupled with activation of oximic hydroxyl group by Sn^{II} facilitates generation of aryl cyanide from aldoxime. These results are exhibited in Table 3.

However, the rupture of the oxime to aldehyde could not be totally eliminated under this reaction condition.

Table 3. Conversion of aldoximes to primary amides with SnCl₂·2H₂O under basic conditions

The reaction scheme shows piperonal oxime (**2**) reacting with SnCl₂·2H₂O and a base to produce piperonal amide (**2a**) and piperonal aldehyde (**2b**).

Entry	SnCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (mmol)	Base (1 mmol)	Solvent additive, if any	Reaction ^a time (h)	Yield ^b of amide 2a (%)	Yield ^b of aldehyde 2b (%)
1	1	-	CH ₃ CN	0.5	-	80
2	1	DBU	Toluene	2	75	15
3	1	DBU	Toluene	3	82	8
4	1	DBU	Toluene 4 Å MS	7 ^c	30	-
5	1	DBU	CH ₃ CN	16	60	-
6	1	Et ₃ N	CH ₃ CN	8	-	-
7	1	Et ₃ N	Toluene	8	40	60
8	1	Pyridine	Toluene	3	30	70

^aReaction conditions : Reactions were carried out on one millimolar scale in dry toluene/other dry solvents (3 mL/mmol) under refluxing conditions.

^bRefers to isolated yield upon column chromatographic purification.

^c3,4-Methylenedioxybenzoxime was isolated in 40% yield.

This transformation was explored for a range of aldoximes and the results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Transformation of aldoximes to amides with $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and DBU

Entry	Substrate	Time ^a (h)	Yield ^b of primary amide (%)	Yield ^b of aldehyde (%)
1		3	82	8
2		12	60	20
3		8	50	40
4		10	70	20
5		8	65	25
6		12	40	50
7		16	70	25
8		8	75	20
9		7	50	40
10		10	85	10
11		8	72	20
12		20	65	10

^aReaction conditions : $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mmol), DBU (2 mmol), dry toluene (6 mL), reflux.

^bRefers to isolated yield after chromatographic purification; the primary amides and aldehydes are known products with physical and spectral properties that agreed closely with those reported in literature.

Deoxygenation was always found to be a competing process and it was particularly so when the aromatic ring bears a hydroxy group at *ortho/para*-position. Attempt to circumvent this problem by exposing **2** to the present reagent combination in the presence of 4 Å MS in toluene

under reflux for a protracted period of 7 h provided **2a** in a poor yield of 30%. Significantly, 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoxime was isolated in 40% yield from the reaction mixture. The result is in sharp contrast to facilitatory role of 4 Å MS in the case of ketoximes and may be attributed to the removal of loose water molecule of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the molecular sieve which was crucially needed for controlled hydration of the aryl cyanide to amide.

To summarize, a protocol for high throughput conversion of ketoximes to corresponding anilides has been developed using 1 mol equivalent of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and TBAI (10 mol%) in dry CH_3CN containing 4 Å MS under reflux conditions. Aldoximes were also transformed to primary amides with equimolar amounts of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and DBU in dry toluene at reflux temperature together with varying amounts of aldehyde precursors. Expedient and highly selective Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes with these readily available, inexpensive reagents under operationally simple conditions adds to synthetic utility of the protocol.

Experimental

Stannous chloride dihydrate, tetrabutylammonium iodide and DBU were procured from E. Merck, India. IR and NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer FTIR L120-000A and Bruker AM-300L (300 MHz), Bruker DPX-400 (400 MHz) instruments. Silica gel (60–120 mesh, Spectrochem, India) was used for column chromatography. Melting points were determined by open capillary method in metal bath and are uncorrected. Light petrol used refers to the fraction boiling at 60–80 °C.

Amides show a strong band for the C=O group that appears in the range of 1630–1680 cm^{-1} . Secondary amides have one -NH stretching band at *ca.* 3300 cm^{-1} . Primary amides (-NH₂) gives two characteristic bands near 3350 and 3180 cm^{-1} .

Typical procedure of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -TBAI-mediated Beckmann rearrangement of acetophenone oxime to acetanilide :

To a solution of acetophenone oxime (270 mg, 2 mmol) in dry acetonitrile (6 mL) in a round bottomed flask was added $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (450 mg, ~2 mmol), TBAI (73 mg, ~0.2 mmol) and 4 Å MS (40 mg) and the mixture was heated at reflux for 30 min in an oil bath (TLC monitor-

ing). To the cooled reaction mixture was added saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (6 mL) and it was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 7 mL). The combined organic extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give the crude product. It was chromatographed over silica gel (100–120 mesh) using EtOAc-*n*-hexane (1 : 4) as eluent to afford pure acetanilide (265 mg, ~98%), m.p. 110–112 °C (lit.³³ 112 °C). It was characterized from spectral features (FTIR, ¹H NMR) and comparison (TLC, mixed m.p.) with an authentic sample of acetanilide.

A typical SnCl₂·2H₂O/DBU-catalyzed one-pot synthesis of primary amide :

A solution of piperonal oxime (345 mg, ~2.1 mmol) in dry toluene (6 mL) was treated with SnCl₂·2H₂O (472 mg, ~2.1 mmol) and DBU (320 mg, ~2.1 mmol) and the mixture was heated at reflux for 3 h. After completion of the reaction, as indicated by TLC, saturated ice-cold NaHCO₃ solution (3 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and it was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 10 mL). The combined organic extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and solvent was removed at reduced pressure to give the crude product. The product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using EtOAc-*n*-hexane (3 : 2) as eluent to afford 3,4-methylene-dioxybenzamide (283 mg, ~82%), m.p. 161–163 °C (lit.³³ 162 °C). A small amount of piperonal was also isolated (25 mg, ~8%), m.p. 36–38 °C (lit.³³ 37 °C).

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